

Renewable Energy in Cycling Infrastructure: Acceptance and potential of a photovoltaic-covered bike path on Mahé (Seychelles)

Marco Buck
Benno Rothstein

Introduction to the study

The global energy sector is undergoing a critical transition, driven by rising demand, the impacts of climate change, and geopolitical disruptions such as the COVID-19 pandemic and the war in Ukraine. These crises have reinforced the dependency on fossil fuels and exposed the vulnerability of international energy markets (IRENA, 2023; REN21, 2023). In line with the Paris Climate Agreement, limiting global warming to 1.5°C requires global CO₂ emissions to reach net zero by 2050, with the energy sector – responsible for 75.7% of emissions through electricity, heat, and transport – at the core of decarbonization efforts (GE et al., 2024).

Tropical countries face additional challenges, as energy demand continues to grow with demographic and economic development. For Seychelles, electricity demand is projected to increase to 875 GWh annually by 2030, alongside an additional peak load of 65 MW (IRENA, 2023; Brown et al., 2016). As a Small Island Developing State (SIDS), the country is characterized by geographic isolation, limited natural resources, and strong dependence on imports, which heightens exposure to global energy-price fluctuations and external shocks. Currently, over 95% of its energy supply derives from imported fossil fuels, creating high economic and environmental costs (Government of Seychelles, 2019). In response, national policy aims to raise the share of renewable energy to 15% by 2030 (PUC, n.d.).

In this context, innovative solutions that integrate energy and transport systems are essential. Photovoltaic (PV)-covered bike paths represent a novel approach, combining electricity generation with sustainable mobility by roofing cycling routes with solar panels. Beyond supplying renewable power, such infrastructure offers functional benefits including weather protection and safety improvements. Internationally, reference projects have been implemented in South Korea, India, Switzerland, and Germany, demonstrating the dual potential of clean energy generation and climate-friendly transport.

Despite these examples, feasibility and acceptance studies remain absent in tropical regions and SIDS. This constitutes a significant research gap, given the unique socio-economic conditions, climatic challenges, and infrastructure limitations faced by island states.

Addressing this gap is crucial to assess whether PV-covered bike paths can contribute meaningfully to energy diversification, greenhouse-gas reduction, and sustainable mobility transitions in such contexts.

This study therefore explores the applicability of PV-covered bike paths in Seychelles. By situating the analysis within global energy-transition debates while focusing on a tropical island case study, the research contributes empirical insights to an underrepresented context.

Objective of the investigation

This study investigates the public acceptance and potential of a PV-covered bike path in Seychelles, a representative case of a tropical island nation. On Mahé, the main island, growing traffic demand, limited infrastructure, and the need for sustainable transport solutions create a critical context for assessing innovative mobility concepts.

The research addresses three interconnected objectives. First, it examines local perceptions and acceptance of a PV-covered bike path through a structured survey, capturing anticipated benefits, opportunities, and potential concerns. Second, it evaluates transport feasibility by conducting traffic counts along the proposed corridor between Victoria and Providence, providing empirical insight into commuter patterns and potential demand. Third, the study considers the integration of renewable energy, assessing the path's capacity to generate electricity while providing functional benefits such as weather protection.

By combining social, transport, and energy perspectives, the study offers a comprehensive assessment of the feasibility and impact of PV-covered bike paths, providing evidence to inform sustainable mobility and renewable energy strategies in tropical island contexts.

Introduction of research area

This study focuses on a selected corridor on Mahé, the main island of Seychelles, examining its geographical, infrastructural, and socio-economic characteristics in the context of sustainable mobility. Mahé presents significant potential for innovative transportation solutions due to its tropical climate, urbanization patterns, and increasing traffic volumes, which contribute to congestion and environmental pollution, particularly on routes leading to the capital, Victoria (Krütli et al., 2022).

Seychelles was chosen as a representative case for exploring sustainable transport concepts, as the nation faces challenges common to tropical and small island developing states,

including climate-change impacts and limited infrastructure. A notable example of sustainable mobility within the archipelago is La Digue, where bicycles are the primary mode of transport, demonstrating the feasibility of a near-complete transition to low-emission mobility under suitable conditions. In contrast, private vehicle use on Mahé is high, leading to commuter congestion, time losses, and elevated emissions.

The study specifically examines the approximately 5.3 km corridor connecting Victoria with the industrial area of Providence (see Figure 1). This route was selected based on its low gradient – less than ten meters of elevation change – making it highly suitable for cycling infrastructure (Google Earth; Komoot). Providence, as the largest industrial zone, generates substantial commuter traffic, providing both a practical testbed for sustainable mobility interventions and potential for measurable reductions in congestion and CO₂ emissions. The route’s topography and commuter patterns make it particularly appropriate for assessing the feasibility and societal acceptance of PV-covered bike paths, with potential co-benefits for public health and quality of life in the surrounding communities.

Figure 1: Possible route of the PV-covered bike path between Victoria and Providence
(Source: Google Maps 2025)

For a more detailed analysis and assessment, the route was divided into four sections, each characterized by different infrastructural conditions, usage intensity and surrounding land use. These sections are illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Overview of the sections for possible route of the PV-covered bike path between Victoria and Providence
(Source: Google Maps 2025)

Section A (0 to A): This segment begins at the roundabout near the Unity Monument in Victoria (coordinates: -4.627278, 55.455155) and extends to the roundabout at the STC Hypermarket (coordinates: -4.630387, 55.460582). It starts in the urban centre and covers approximately 800 m. The first 400 m cover a three-lane configuration: two lanes lead into Victoria while one lane heads towards Providence. After this point, the outbound direction toward Providence is expanded into two lanes, resulting in a four-lane road with two lanes in each direction. Throughout the entire section, pavements are present on both sides of the road. These pavements are mostly continuous, but are interrupted in some areas, as shown in Figure 3. Additionally, an access road is integrated into the traffic layout on the left side.

Figure 3: Section A – Route segment from Unity Monument to STC Hypermarket
 (Source: Own pictures)

Section B (A to B): This section extends from the roundabout at STC Hypermarket (coordinates: -4.630387, 55.460582) to the roundabout in the Plaisance area (coordinates: -4.635140, 55.465693). It covers approximately 800 m with a continuous four-lane roadway, featuring open spaces and a pavement in some areas. Existing obstacles, shown in Figure 4, include a crossing with a railing and an access road where pedestrians cannot cross.

Figure 4: Section B – Route segment from STC Hypermarket to Plaisance roundabout
 (Source: Own pictures)

Section C (B to C): This section stretches from the Plaisance roundabout (coordinates: -4.635140, 55.465693) to the roundabout at Eden Island (coordinates: -4.642231, 55.473179). The route is approximately 1.2 km long features a continuous four-lane roadway and is accompanied by a pavement running alongside, which is separated from the roadway by a metal railing. Along this segment, open areas alternate with densely built property boundaries and walls. While the pavement is generally well-constructed and

paved, in certain places its width is restricted by walls, traffic signs, drainage channels or railings, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Section C – Route segment from Plaisance roundabout to Eden Island roundabout
(Source: Own pictures)

Section D (C to D): This final part of the route extends from the roundabout at Eden Island (coordinates: -4.642231, 55.473179) to the roundabout in the industrial area of Providence (coordinates: -4.656778, 55.487000). This 2.4 km segment runs mostly along a four-lane main road with several entry and exit points. The narrow, uneven pedestrian path is partly

unpaved, occasionally forcing pedestrians onto the verge or grassy areas, with physical separation from traffic only in a few spots. A critical point is a two-lane bridge with no walkway, creating a major safety risk and limiting potential route development (Figures 6 and 7).

Figure 6: Section D (1/2) – Route segment from Eden Island roundabout to Providence roundabout
(Source: Own pictures)

Figure 7: Section D (2/2)– Route segment from Eden Island roundabout to Providence roundabout
 (Source: Own pictures)

Table 1 provides an overview of the individual sections. Point 0 to A corresponds to Section A, Point A to B corresponds to section B, Point B to C corresponds to Section C and Point C to D corresponds to Section D.

Table 1: Overview of the individual sections of the possible route

Section	Approx. Length	Characteristic	Challenges
A (0 to A)	0.8km	Dense development, high traffic volume	Limited space
B (A to B)	0.8km	Open spaces	Complex traffic layout
C (B to C)	1.2km	Existing pavement	Narrow sections in places
D (C to D)	2.4km	Small ways with trees	Narrow two-lane bridge

Research methodology

This study employed a mixed-methods approach to investigate the public acceptance and potential feasibility of a PV-covered bike path on Mahé, the main island of Seychelles. The methodology focuses on the materials, procedures, and execution of data collection, combining two complementary quantitative methods: a structured survey and manual traffic counts. The survey, as the primary data source, received more detailed attention due to its complexity and the depth of information obtained. The traffic count served as a supplementary observational tool, providing empirical context regarding commuter behaviour and transport demand.

Survey

Survey implementation

Data collection occurred between March and April, 2025. Two distribution modes were employed: paper-based surveys and online surveys via Google Forms. The survey targeted residents, commuters, and students within the study area, spanning the capital city Victoria and the industrial zone of Providence on Mahé. This corridor was selected as the proposed route for the PV-covered bike path, given its mix of commuter and industrial traffic, as well as its strategic relevance for mobility studies.

Participation was voluntary. Paper-based respondents included pedestrians at bus stops, employees in the Providence industrial area, and students and staff from the Seychelles

Institute of Technology (SIT) and the Seychelles Maritime Academy (SMA). Prior to completing the survey, participants were presented with visual materials illustrating existing international PV-covered bike path projects and a sample design adapted for Seychelles. Digital participants accessed the same visual materials through the Google Forms platform.

A total of 115 surveys were returned: 53 paper-based and 62 online. Five incomplete paper-based questionnaires were excluded, leaving a final dataset of 110 fully-completed responses. All paper responses were digitized to ensure uniform data analysis. This dataset formed the basis for subsequent statistical evaluation and interpretation.

Survey research method

The survey was designed to measure societal acceptance, defined as the positive or tolerant attitude of individuals towards normative principles, technical systems, or innovative products, expressed both cognitively and through behavioural intent (Brockhaus Enzyklopädie, n.d.; Quiring, 2006). Acceptance is a key determinant for the potential success of novel infrastructure such as PV-covered bike paths, as it can influence actual usage patterns and adoption rates.

Quantitative survey research was selected due to the lack of prior studies on the acceptance of PV infrastructure in Seychelles. Surveys allow systematic and standardized data collection, producing generalizable and comparable findings on social attitudes, behaviours, and perceptions (Döring, 2023; Creswell and Creswell, 2018). The survey used primarily closed questions, complemented by three 5-point Likert-scale items, which enable the measurement of latent attitudes and subjective perceptions (Joshi et al., 2015). Data collected included attitudinal, behavioural, and descriptive dimensions, with a primary focus on participant acceptance and demographic characteristics.

The quantitative approach employed is rooted in the experimental and measurement paradigms of social science, tracing back to the institutionalization of psychology in the late 19th century, particularly the work of Wilhelm Wundt (Döring, 2023). This method facilitates objective, reliable, and reproducible results suitable for evidence-based policy and infrastructure planning.

Sample design and pretesting

A pretest was conducted with ten English-proficient participants in Germany to evaluate question clarity, response options, and estimated completion time. Feedback from the pretest informed final adjustments, ensuring that the survey would be comprehensible, concise, and feasible for participants in Seychelles. The finalized questionnaire was prepared entirely in Germany prior to field deployment, due to time constraints and logistical limitations on Mahé.

Questionnaire structure

The questionnaire comprised fifteen items, organized into three main sections:

- ◆ *Socio-demographic characteristics:* Gender, age, and educational attainment, providing context for the analysis of attitudes toward the proposed bike path.
- ◆ *Current transportation behaviour and potential of the bike path:* Ownership of bicycles, frequency of public transport usage, perceived challenges of cycling in Mahé (e.g., infrastructure, climate, terrain), and perceived benefits and disadvantages of a PV-covered bike path. Responses regarding challenges, benefits, and disadvantages were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from ‘Strongly Disagree’ to ‘Strongly Agree’ (Table 2). The specific answer options for challenges, benefits and disadvantages are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Challenges, benefits and disadvantages answer options

Challenges	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Weak cycling infrastructure (e.g. bike lanes, parking spaces) ◆ Unsafe road conditions ◆ Hot climate and little shade ◆ Regular heavy rainfall ◆ Hilly terrain ◆ Bikes are difficult to obtain or expensive ◆ Other transport options (e.g. car, bus) are more convenient ◆ Safety concerns (accidents, thefts) 	
Benefits	Disadvantages
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Protection from sun ◆ Protection from rain ◆ Dual land use ◆ Cycling would be more attractive ◆ Improved infrastructure for cyclists (dedicated bike lanes) ◆ Solar panels would contribute to a sustainable energy production ◆ Reduction of car traffic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Construction costs ◆ Impact on the nature and landscape of Mahé ◆ Maintenance ◆ Safety problems due to improper use by pedestrians or motorbikes ◆ Potential necessity to cut down trees to avoid shading or damage to the PV system ◆ Construction could lead to resistance among the population

- ◆ *Environmental awareness and technology acceptance:* Attitudes towards renewable energy, sustainable transport adoption, potential use of a PV-covered bike path, and support for public funding or a bike-sharing system. Participants were also provided an open-ended option for additional comments.

This design allowed a comprehensive evaluation of both behavioural intentions and attitudinal acceptance, while also capturing participants' environmental awareness and perceptions of technological innovation.

Traffic counting

Traffic count methodology

Traffic counting was conducted as a supplementary quantitative observation to measure commuter traffic volumes along the proposed bike path corridor. Manual traffic counting was chosen for its objectivity, low cost, and minimal influence on participant behaviour (Vallée et al., 2021). Counts were conducted on 26 and 27 March 2025, at the Providence roundabout (4°39'24.4"S, 55°29'13.0"E), a central access point connecting Victoria with the industrial zone. This location enabled observation of inbound and outbound traffic flows and provided a representative assessment of commuting potential.

Observation protocol

Traffic counts were conducted during peak commuting hours: 6:00-9:30 a.m. and 2:00-5:30 p.m. (Krütli et al., 2022; Schaniel, 2022). Vehicles and commuters were recorded at ten-minute intervals using the mobile app *Zähler*, allowing systematic categorization into cars, trucks, motorcycles/scooters, buses, and pedestrians. Observations accounted for inbound traffic from Victoria in the morning and outbound traffic from Providence in the afternoon. Weather conditions were deemed negligible due to the absence of cycling activity in the area. A minor portion of inbound morning traffic may have been missed due to an alternative entry route.

Counting locations

Two observation points were selected to maximize coverage of traffic flows. The morning observation focused on the Providence Highway bus stop, capturing vehicles entering the industrial area via the first exit from Victoria. The afternoon observation was conducted near the ABSA Providence Branch, covering outbound traffic toward Victoria via the third exit. These strategic locations provided the most comprehensive view of commuting behaviour while minimizing double counting.

Data analysis procedures

Survey data analysis: Survey responses were digitized and analysed using descriptive statistical methods. Descriptive statistics – including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations – were calculated to summarize sociodemographic characteristics, current transportation behaviour, and attitudes toward PV-covered bike paths. Likert-scale items were treated as ordinal variables, allowing calculation of mean scores and standard deviations for individual items and thematic clusters.

Traffic count analysis: Traffic count data were aggregated by time interval and vehicle category. Peak and off-peak volumes were identified to characterize commuter patterns along the proposed bike path corridor. Data were visualized using flow diagrams and tables to illustrate hourly traffic distribution and modal composition. These analyses provided empirical evidence of potential user demand, informing the feasibility of a dedicated cycling infrastructure in the selected corridor.

Integration of survey and traffic data: Combined analysis of survey and traffic data facilitated a holistic assessment of the project's feasibility. Survey-derived acceptance measures were cross-referenced with traffic volume data to evaluate whether public support aligns with practical commuter potential. This integrated approach allowed identification of sections where infrastructure investment could yield the greatest benefit and provided evidence for targeted recommendations on route design and public engagement strategies.

Overall, this methodological framework ensures a comprehensive, evidence-based evaluation of both social and infrastructural dimensions, supporting informed decision-making for the implementation of PV-covered bike paths in tropical island contexts.

Results

Survey

The following section presents the results of the survey. For clarity, the findings have been organized thematically into four categories: Socio-demographic data, use of current transportation on Mahé, potential for a bike path and environmental awareness and technology acceptance. The data analysis was conducted using Excel, Google Forms and Google Sheets. The results are based on 110 fully completed questionnaires.

Socio Demographic Data

First, it is important to look at the demographic background in the results. For a better understanding of the participants who took part in the survey.

Seventy-four participants (67.3%) of the survey are male, while 36 (32.7%) are female. The option 'Diverse' was not selected by any participant as you can see in Figure 8. This shows male participants are more represented in the survey sample.

Figure 8: Distribution by gender
(n = 110)

Figure 9 shows the age distribution of the participants. Due to the high participation rate of students from the SIT and the SMA, a relatively high proportion of respondents are under the age of twenty. Based on 109 valid age responses, the mean age (arithmetic average) of the participants is 23.95 years.

Formula 1: Arithmetic average

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i$$

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{109} \sum_{i=1}^{109} x_i = \frac{2611}{109} = 23.95$$

Figure 9: Number of age distribution
(n = 109)

The number of age distribution shows a clear concentration on the youngest age group. Sixty-nine respondents (62.7%) are under the age of twenty. The second-largest group consists of 20- to 29-year-olds, with nineteen participants (17.3%). The age group 30- to 39-years is represented by nine individuals (8.3%), while the age groups 40- to 49- years and 50- to 59- years are represented by five participants (4.6%) each. Only two participants (1.8%) were 60 years or older. This shows that participants with and over the age of 30 are presented with around 19.3%.

Regarding the educational background, most of the respondents reported having completed upper secondary education: 89 individuals (80.9%) indicated holding an upper secondary qualification. A total of seventeen participants (15.5%) reported having an academic degree (Bachelor's, Master's or PhD). Only three individuals (2.7%) had completed lower secondary education as their highest level of formal education, and one respondent indicated having no formal schooling. These results suggest that the survey sample overall reflects a generally high level of education.

Use of current transportation on Mahé

In response to the question about bike ownership, 69 out of 110 respondents (62.7%) answered 'No', while 41 individuals (37.3%) answered 'Yes' for owning a bike. This indicates that around one third of the participants own a bike.

Figure 10 shows the results about the most-used modes of daily transportation among respondents. Multiple answers were allowed for this question. The results show that 'Public transport' with 83 answers (75.5%) and 'Car' with 78 answers (70.9%) have the biggest impact among the current transportation modes. 'Walking' with 51 answers (46.4%) also plays a significant role in the daily transportation. In contrast, other modes of transport such as 'Private transport service' with seventeen (15.5%), 'Carpooling' with fifteen (13.6%), 'Motorcycle' with ten (9.1%) and 'Bicycle' with eight (7.3%) answers were mentioned far less frequently. These options appear to play only a marginal role in respondents' daily commuting habits and are rarely used as their main mean of transport.

Figure 10: Preferred main transportation modes in Mahé
(multiple choice; n = 110)

The use of public transportation per week is shown in Figure 11. Respondents reported that 46 of them (42%) are using it 'Daily', while 30 respondents (27%) said they use it 'Often' (4-6 times per week). In contrast, a smaller proportion of participants reported using public transportation 'Rarely' (8%) or 'Sometimes' (10%). Only 13% of respondents said that they 'Never' use public transport.

Figure 11: Use of public transportation per week
(n = 110)

Potential for a bike path

This section presents the results of the Likert scale. It focuses on the challenges associated with the existing infrastructure. Subsequently, the results regarding the perceived benefits and disadvantages of a PV-covered bike path are shown.

The numbers indicate the frequency of responses for each scale point: from ‘Strongly disagree’ (1), ‘Disagree’ (2), ‘Neutral’ (3), ‘Agree’ (4) to ‘Strongly agree’ (5). The mean value for each question is highlighted with a blue background. A high mean value reflects a strong agreement among participants, while a low mean value reflects a low agreement. Additionally, the scale point with the highest number of responses is highlighted in red.

The mean value of the challenges examined (see Table 3) is between 2.82 to 4.14. The most significant issues identified are ‘Weak cycling infrastructure’ (4.14), ‘Unsafe road conditions’ (4.07), ‘Safety concerns’ (3.97) and ‘Hot climate and little shade’ (3.76). The challenges with the lowest mean value are ‘Bikes are difficult to obtain or expensive’ (2.82) and ‘Regular heavy rainfall’ (3.21).

Table 3: Overview of the results of the participants ratings regarding the given challenges

Challenges	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neutral (3)	Agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)	Mean
Weak cycling infrastructure (e.g. bike lanes, parking spaces)	5	8	12	27	58	4.14
Unsafe road conditions	4	6	13	42	45	4.07
Hot climate and little shade	3	9	30	37	31	3.76
Regular heavy rainfall	3	11	65	22	9	3.21
Hilly terrain	5	5	36	46	18	3.61
Bikes are difficult to obtain or expensive	15	27	39	21	8	2.82
Other transport options (e.g. car, bus) are more convenient	4	7	28	45	26	3.75
Safety concerns (accidents, thefts)	4	2	24	43	37	3.97

(n = 110)

Table 4 shows the benefits expected from a PV-covered bike path according to the respondents. The mean value of the benefits is between 3.75 and 4.16. All items have a generally high mean value. The most significant benefits are ‘Solar panels would contribute to a sustainable energy production’ (4.16), ‘Improved infrastructure for cyclists’ (4.09), closely followed by ‘Protection from sun’ and ‘Reduction of car traffic’ with (3.89).

Table 4: Overview of the results of the participants ratings regarding the given benefits

Benefits	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neutral (3)	Agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)	Mean
Protection from sun	4	5	24	43	34	3.89
Protection from rain	4	6	29	41	30	3.79
Dual land use	2	5	35	41	27	3.78
Cycling would be more attractive	2	8	37	31	32	3.75
Improved infrastructure for cyclists (dedicated bike lanes)	2	3	19	45	41	4.09
Solar panels would contribute to a sustainable energy production	1	5	23	27	54	4.16
Reduction of car traffic	7	5	26	27	45	3.89

(n=110)

Table 5 shows the mentioned disadvantages of a PV-covered bike path. The mean value of the disadvantages is between 3.24 and 3.82. The most significant disadvantages are ‘Safety problems due to improper use by pedestrians or motorbikes’ (3.82), ‘Construction costs’ (3.75) and ‘Maintenance’ (3.68). The disadvantages with the lowest mean value are ‘Impact on the nature and landscape of Mahé’ (3.28) and ‘Construction could lead to resistance among the population’ (3.38).

Table 5: Overview of the results of the participants ratings regarding the given disadvantages

Disadvantages	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neutral (3)	Agree (4)	Strongly agree (5)	Mean
Construction costs	3	5	29	53	20	3.75
Impact on the nature and landscape of Mahé	11	14	38	32	15	3.24
Maintenance	1	10	33	45	21	3.68
Safety problems due to improper use by pedestrians or motorbikes	2	6	29	46	27	3.82
Potential necessity to cut down trees to avoid shading or damage to the PV system	5	15	25	39	26	3.60
Construction could lead to resistance among the population	5	12	45	32	16	3.38

(n=110)

Pedestrians were also asked how they feel about promoting cycling as a daily way of transportation. Forty-one individuals (37.3%) rated it as ‘Very positive’, while 34 participants (30.9%) rated it as ‘Positive’. Twenty-three individuals (20.9%) had a ‘Neutral’ position. Only nine respondents (8.2%) had a ‘Negative’ opinion on cycling, with just three individuals (2.7%) rating it as ‘Very negative’. This means that 75 respondents (68.2%) feel ‘Positive’ or ‘Very positive’, while twelve (10.9%) feel ‘Negative’ or ‘Very negative’ about cycling. Overall, the results indicate a mostly positive view of cycling as a means of transport.

Environmental awareness and technology acceptance

In response to the question whether participants would cycle more frequently if the infrastructure were improved, 47 individuals (42.7%) selected ‘Strongly agree’, while 29 individuals (26.4%) chose ‘Agree’. 22 participants (20.0%) responded ‘Neutral’, while eight participants (7.3%) selected ‘Disagree’ and four individuals (3.6%) ‘Strongly disagree’. The responses show a generally high level of agreement with the idea that better infrastructure could lead to more frequent bike usage.

Figure 12 shows the relevance of sustainable energy sources for the pedestrians. A total of 84.5% rated their importance as either ‘Very important’ or ‘Important’, a small proportion chose ‘Neutral’ (12.7%) and ‘Less important’ (2.7%), while no respondent chose ‘Not important at all’.

Figure 12: Relevance of sustainable energy sources
(n = 110)

When asked, if public funds should be invested to build up a PV-covered bike path, 56 participants (50.9%) answered ‘Yes’, while fourteen (12.7%) answered ‘No’. A total of 40 individuals (36.4%) said they were ‘Unsure’.

Figure 13 shows whether they would use a PV-covered bike path. More than two-thirds stated that they would be ‘Very likely’ (39%) or ‘Likely’ (28%) to use such infrastructure. 22% responded with ‘Neutral’ and only a small number of participants answered with ‘Unlikely’ (9%) or ‘Very unlikely’ (2%). The results show a high level of acceptance and willingness to use a PV-covered bike path.

Figure 13: Willingness to use a PV-covered bike path
(n = 110)

Finally, Figure 14 represents the attitude of the respondents towards a public bike-sharing system. More than 60% of respondents indicated, that they could imagine using such a service. Around 20% responded neutrally, while a small proportion of 19% said they are unlikely to use it or do not consider it to be relevant. Overall, the distribution of responses indicates a positive tendency towards public bike-sharing services.

Figure 14: Willingness to use a public bike-sharing system
(n = 110)

The participants had the opportunity to write down some further suggestions. Thirty-seven individuals out of the 110 used this opportunity. The additional comments reveal four key insights. Many participants view the cycling project as innovative, health-promoting and environmentally friendly, and especially appreciate the weather protection and potential cost savings. However, some expressed personal barriers like lack of need, safety concerns or not being able to ride a bike. Mixed responses highlight that factors like topography, climate and feasibility influence acceptance, with the project seen as more realistic in specific areas like Victoria and Providence. Several practical suggestions were also made regarding infrastructure such as safe bike lanes, dedicated parking spaces and shaded paths. Overall, the feedback reflects both, strong support and realistic concerns.

Traffic counting

Wednesday morning

The manual traffic count was conducted at the Providence roundabout on Wednesday 26 March 2025, between 6:00 and 9:30 a.m. A total of 961 vehicles and individuals were counted during this period. Of these, 810 were vehicles (84.3%) and 151 (15.7%) were individuals getting off arriving buses at the *Providence Highway Bus Stop* during the observation period.

Passenger cars dominated the morning traffic, accounting for 670 vehicles (82.7%). Followed by 102 trucks (12.6%), 22 motorcycles (2.7%), and sixteen buses (2%).

The average traffic volume interval was approximately 38.6 vehicles per ten-minute interval (see Figure 15). Between 8:30 and 9:00 a.m. there was a considerable increase in traffic, with 165 vehicles being registered. During this thirty-minute period, 147 cars, eleven trucks, four scooters and three buses were recorded. It is important to note for all traffic volume figures, that bus passengers were not included in the general traffic volume, as their inclusion would have significantly distorted the results; because buses arrive at fixed intervals and often release large groups of passengers at once, which does not reflect the continuous traffic flow.

Figure 15: Traffic volume 26.03.2025 from 6 a.m. to 9:30 a.m.

Thursday morning

On Thursday 27 March 2025, the traffic count was conducted again, applying the same conditions as the day before. The traffic count was carried out from 6:00 to 9:30 a.m. at the Providence roundabout. A total of 1,022 units were recorded, of which 859 vehicles and 163 people were counted. All the 163 people got off arriving buses at the *Providence Highway Bus Stop*.

Passenger cars accounted for most of the traffic with a number of 707 vehicles (82.3%). These were followed by 117 trucks (13.6%), 22 motorcycles (2.6%), and thirteen buses (1.5%).

The average traffic volume was 40.9 vehicles per ten-minute interval (see Figure 16). The highest traffic volume was recorded between 9:00 and 9:30 a.m., with 164 vehicles counted in total, including 133 passenger cars, 24 trucks, five motorcycles, and two buses.

Figure 16: Traffic volume 27.03.2025 from 6 a.m. to 9:30 a.m.

Comparison of the two morning counts

Table 6 displays a comparison of the two traffic counts conducted on Wednesday 26 and Thursday 27 March 2025. The table reveals a similar overall distribution of traffic categories, with a slightly higher total volume on the second counting day. While 961 units were recorded on Wednesday, consisting of 810 vehicles and 151 bus passengers, Thursday's count amounted to 1,022 units, consisting of 859 vehicles and 163 bus passengers. This represents an increase of 61 units, corresponding to a percentage rise of about 6.35% compared to Wednesday.

The number of passenger cars increased by 5.5%, from 670 to 707. A notable increase was also observed in the number of trucks, rising from 102 to 117 (+14.7%). The number of motorcycles remained constant at 22. The number of buses decreased slightly, from sixteen to thirteen, while the number of bus passengers increased from 151 to 163 (+7.9%).

The average traffic volume per ten-minute interval was 38.6 vehicles on Wednesday and 40.9 vehicles on Thursday, highlighting a generally higher traffic density on the second observation day. The highest traffic density on both days occurred during a thirty-minute interval towards the end of the observation period:

- Wednesday: 8:30-9:00 a.m. with 165 vehicles
- Thursday: 9:00-9:30 a.m. with 164 vehicles

The interval with the lowest traffic volume is identical on both days, between 6:00 and 6:10 a.m., with only ten vehicles recorded. While on Wednesday, traffic density increased sharply after 6:30 a.m., on Thursday, it increased gradually and continuously until the peak shortly before 9:30 a.m.

Table 6: Comparison of traffic volumes and composition on 26 and 27 March 2025 in the morning

Category	Wednesday morning 26.03.2025	Thursday morning 27.03.2025	Difference	Change [%]
Cars	670	707	37	+5.52 %
Trucks	102	117	15	+14.71 %
Motorcycles	22	22	±0	0.00 %
Buses	16	13	-3	-18.75 %
Bus passengers	151	163	12	+7.95 %
Total units	961	1,022	61	+6.35 %

Wednesday afternoon

On Wednesday 26 March 2025, the traffic count was conducted in the afternoon, from 2:00 to 5:30 p.m., at the Providence roundabout. The focus was on vehicles entering the roundabout from the Providence industrial area and exiting at the third exit towards Victoria.

A total of 1025 vehicles were recorded during this period. Due to visual limitations in the afternoon, the count focuses only on motorized individual traffic. With 828 passenger cars (80.8%), private car traffic accounted for the largest share again. This was supplemented by 144 trucks (14.0%) and 53 motorcycles (5.2%). The average traffic volume was approximately 39.4 vehicles per ten-minute interval. Overall, the traffic volume appeared steady, with only moderate fluctuations (see Figure 17).

Figure 17: Traffic volume 26.03.2025 from 2 p.m. to 5:30 p.m.

Thursday afternoon

On Thursday 28 March 2025, the traffic count was conducted again under the same conditions as the previous day, from 2:00 to 5:30 p.m. at the Providence roundabout. A total of 963 vehicles was recorded.

Cars accounted for the largest share, with 787 vehicles (81.7%). These were followed by 145 trucks (15.1%) and 31 motorcycles (3.2%). No buses were recorded during the afternoon. The average traffic volume was approximately 37 vehicles per ten-minute interval. The traffic volume (see Figure 18) shows a similar trend to the previous day.

Figure 18: Traffic volume 27.03.2025 from 2 p.m. to 5:30 p.m.

Comparison of the two afternoon counts

Comparing the afternoon traffic counts on Wednesday 26 March and Thursday 27 March 2025, both days reveal an overall similar traffic profile, with small differences in the total volume and vehicle category shares. A total of 1025 vehicles were recorded on Wednesday afternoon, compared to 963 vehicles on Thursday afternoon. This represents a decrease of 62 vehicles, corresponding to a decline of about 6% (see Table 7).

The number of passenger cars decreased by 5% from 828 to 787. The number of trucks remained almost unchanged, increasing from 144 on Wednesday to 145 on Thursday (0.7%). The number of motorcycles decreased significantly by 41.4%, from 53 to 31 vehicles. No buses were recorded on either afternoon.

The average traffic volume per ten-minute interval was 39.4 vehicles on Wednesday and 37.0 vehicles on Thursday. The highest traffic density was observed at different times on each day:

- Wednesday: 2:30-3:00 p.m. with 175 vehicles

- Thursday: 2:20-2:50 p.m. with 191 vehicles

The lowest traffic volume interval on Wednesday was between 5:20 and 5:30 p.m., with only 24 vehicles recorded. While on Thursday it reached between 4:20 and 4:30 p.m.

Table 7: Comparison of traffic volumes and composition on 26 and 27 March 2025 in the afternoon

Category	Wednesday afternoon 26.03.2025	Thursday afternoon 27.03.2025	Difference	Change [%]
Cars	828	787	-41	-5,0 %
Trucks	144	145	1	+0,7 %
Motorcycles	53	31	-22	-41,5 %
Total units	1.025	963	-62	-6,05 %

Interpretation and discussion

The study provides a comprehensive analysis of mobility behaviour and attitudes toward sustainable transportation and technological innovation on Mahé, Seychelles. The survey sample was skewed toward younger respondents, primarily students from SIT and SMA, with a mean age of 23.95 years, compared to the national median of 35 years (National Bureau of Statistics, 2024). While this limits representativeness for the general population, the focus on youth is valuable given their greater openness to ecological, technological, and social innovation, as well as their potential role as early adopters of sustainable infrastructure. Most respondents had completed upper secondary education or higher, suggesting a heightened awareness of environmental and technological issues.

Mobility patterns indicate a dominance of public transport (75.5%) and private cars (70.9%), while cycling plays a marginal role (7.3%), despite 37.3% bike ownership. Low cycling rates are attributed primarily to structural barriers, including inadequate infrastructure (mean 4.14), unsafe roads (4.07), and safety concerns (3.97), compounded by climatic and cultural factors consistent with previous research on tropical cycling contexts (Lee and Pojani, 2019).

Feedback on a PV-covered bike path was broadly positive, highlighting key functional benefits such as improved infrastructure for cyclists (4.09), weather protection (sun: 3.89; rain: 3.79), and dual land use for energy generation (3.78), as well as ecological advantages, including renewable energy production (4.16) and potential reductions in motorized transport (3.89). Concerns centred on safety risks due to mixed traffic (3.82), construction costs (3.75), and maintenance requirements (3.68), were consistent with international

findings emphasizing safety-focused design and transparent cost structures (Pascual-Muñoz et al., 2023; Teh et al., 2021). Responses to a potential public bike-sharing system were mixed, reflecting limited local experience, though international examples demonstrate that such programs can increase cycling adoption (Fosgerau et al., 2023; Merforth, 2023; Plasencia-Lozano, 2021).

Manual traffic counts along the 5.3 km Victoria-Providence corridor confirmed consistently high commuter volumes, particularly during peak hours, supporting the route's suitability for dedicated cycling infrastructure. The results suggest that implementing a PV-covered bike path could provide weather-protected, eco-friendly alternatives, reduce congestion, and generate renewable energy, aligning functional benefits with ecological goals.

Methodologically, on-site data collection and the use of visual materials facilitated engagement, yet challenges included limited accessibility to older populations, cultural and language barriers, and a narrow age distribution. Future research should incorporate broader demographic representation, local cultural perspectives, and extended traffic monitoring to improve validity. Economic feasibility remains a key consideration; potential funding models include community-oriented public-private partnerships, allowing shared investment and fostering local engagement (Land Nordrhein-Westfalen, 2006).

Overall, the findings indicate that a PV-covered bike path on Mahé could enhance sustainable mobility, support renewable energy targets, and serve as a model for incremental infrastructure expansion, provided that safety, economic, and cultural factors are carefully addressed. Early public involvement and pilot programs, including awareness campaigns and potential bike-sharing systems, are recommended to maximize adoption and long-term impact (Walker, 2015).

Conclusion and outlook

This study investigated the acceptance and potential of a PV-covered bike path on Mahé, Seychelles, as a model for tropical-island environments. A mixed-methods approach was employed, combining a structured survey of 110 participants, targeted traffic counts, analysis of international reference projects, and comprehensive literature review. The study aimed to evaluate public perception, assess the feasibility of integrating cycling infrastructure with renewable energy generation, and explore the potential contribution to sustainable mobility and climate mitigation.

Survey results indicate a generally high level of public acceptance for a PV-covered bike path. Participants valued improvements to cycling infrastructure, protection from weather

conditions, and the generation of local renewable electricity. The project was perceived not only as a transport solution but also as a strategic response to climate and energy challenges. At the same time, structural barriers to cycling on Mahé were identified, including weak infrastructure, unsafe road conditions, and climatic factors such as heat and limited shade, corroborating existing literature that emphasizes infrastructural and safety concerns as primary constraints to cycling in tropical contexts (Lee and Pojani, 2019).

Traffic counts along the Victoria-Providence corridor consistently revealed high commuter volumes, highlighting the route's strategic importance and suggesting that a dedicated PV-covered bike path could serve as an effective alternative to private motorized transport. Synergies between transport and energy sectors were evident, though potential challenges were also identified, including safety risks, construction costs, and maintenance requirements. The findings underscore the necessity of public awareness, stakeholder engagement, and context-sensitive design to ensure both technical feasibility and social acceptance.

To facilitate implementation, three key steps are recommended. First, broad and representative public engagement should be conducted through follow-up surveys, emphasizing younger and middle-aged populations likely to use the infrastructure. Second, political anchoring and a holistic approach to cycling infrastructure expansion are essential, ensuring connectivity, safe access, and integration with surrounding networks. A phased pilot in the Victoria region, with favourable topography, could serve as a model for systematic infrastructure development. Third, technical feasibility studies and financing strategies, including potential public-private partnerships, should be pursued to address costs, substructure requirements, and projected energy yields.

In conclusion, the study provides promising initial insights into public attitudes toward PV-covered cycling infrastructure in a tropical-island context. Strategically planned and locally adapted implementation could contribute to sustainable urban mobility, reduce dependence on fossil fuels, and serve as a model for similar initiatives in other tropical regions. Given the diversity of tropical climates and topographies, context-specific research remains essential to design effective, locally tailored solutions.

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Marco Buck holds a Bachelor of Engineering (B.Eng.) in Industrial Engineering with a specialization in Electrical and Information Engineering from the University of Applied Sciences in Konstanz, Germany. Before starting his studies, he completed a vocational training as an industrial mechanic, gaining hands-on experience with mechanical systems and industrial processes. He is currently pursuing a Master's degree in Renewable Energies at TH Köln – University of Applied Sciences, Cologne, Germany. His academic interests lie at the intersection of energy technology and economics, with a focus on integrating innovative renewable energy technologies. He is particularly motivated by projects that enable sustainable, renewable-based development and contribute to the creation of CO₂-neutral islands.

Benno Rothstein completed his Ph.D. (Dr. rerum naturalium) at the University of Trier, Germany, in the area of agricultural soil protection. He currently works as a full Professor of 'Natural Resource Management' at the University of Applied Sciences in Konstanz, Germany. He has held successive visiting professorships at the University of Seychelles. His research interests include sustainable energy concepts, adaptation to climate change, vulnerability of infrastructures and competition for water resources. He has written over 110 publications in books and journals and has presented his research results at numerous conferences around the world.

Konstanz University of Applied Sciences (HTWG), Department of Civil Engineering,
Alfred-Wachtel-Straße 8, D-78462 Konstanz, Germany, rothstein@htwg-konstanz.de